

Strategic Plan of Large-Scale Construction Services Company (Case Study at PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi)

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Abstract:- This thesis is qualitative research about analyzing and making short-term and long-term strategic plans for PT Nira Murni Kontruksi as an engineering, procurement and construction services company in purpose for being sustainable and developing. This research attempts to perceive comprehensively any factors that affect the business both internally and externally, using several strategic management analysis tools to formulate strategic alternatives, such as IFE-EFE Matrix (Internal Factor Evaluation and External Factor Evaluation), Competitive Profile Matrix - CPM, SPACE Matrix, Grand Matrix Strategy and SWOT / TOWS Analysis. To determine priorities for the alternative marketing and operational strategies, the Quantitive Strategic Planning Matrix - QSPM decision analysis was carried out. The final research is resulted strategy to continue existing market oil and gas and market development. At the end of the paper, a Strategic Plan with action plans, targets and measures is formulated within the framework of the four perspectives of the Balance Scorecard.

Keywords:- Strategic Management, IFE and EFE, CPM, SPACE Matrix, Grand matrix strategy, SWOT/TOWS, QSPM and Balance Scorecard.

I. INTRODUCTION

The construction service industry is an industry that includes all parties related to the construction process including professional staff, construction implementers and also suppliers who jointly meet the needs of actors in construction. Construction services are services that produce physical infrastructure and facilities. These services include study activities, preparation of technical plans/designs, implementation and supervision and maintenance. Bearing in mind that physical infrastructure and facilities are the foundation of the country's growth, sectors in national development, construction services also play a role as a provider of employment, so construction services are important in national development. The construction industry is one sector that plays an important role in national economic development because of its large contribution to other business sectors (Sudarto et al., 2014). The development of the construction industry will create socio-economic facilities and infrastructure in both developed and developing countries so that it can spur economic growth in other sectors. (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2016).

PT Nira Murni Konstruksi is a national contractor service company engaged in Engineering, Procurement, and Construction (EPC) in the Oil and gas industries, founded in 1996, which was originally a private sub-contractor of a state-owned construction company. PT Nira Murni Konstruksi specializes in engineering, fabrication, maintenance services, contractors and labor suppliers. The main business of the company PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi, namely oil and gas companies such as PT. Medco E&P Indonesia, PT. Conocophillips Indonesia, PT. Chevron Pacific.

Fig. 1: Amount of Construction Companies

Source: BPS, 2021

Based on Figure 1, it is known that the number of construction companies in Indonesia is experiencing high growth. Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), Indonesia's construction companies have reached 203,403 business units. This creates high competition among construction companies in carrying out their business.

In the initial interview in the research conducted on the top management of PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi that currently the company is experiencing many challenges and it is not getting easier from time to time, this condition must be faced now and in the future.

From the initial interview with the top management of PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi although the company has a vision and mission, the strategic plan used to form long-term steps towards the company's vision and mission does not yet exist formally.

PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi with the strategy that has been carried out by the company at this time is quite good, so that the company's existence continues to be sustainable until now, but if you look at the phenomena above, the growth and development of construction service companies is still plagued with quite crucial problems that can interfere with the health of the business, thus disrupting the success of the company. effort. Some very crucial challenges such as increasing competition in the construction industry, low productivity, potential decline in market share and challenges inherent in operational management such as problems with local workers, competence of workers from various areas, the scope of contracts that change suddenly will greatly affect the success of the service company's business, and if left unchecked it will result in the company falling into bankruptcy because the business of a company does not always and only depend on the profits earned but on the level of productivity.

Problems that arise in PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi is stagnation in operating income in recent years, this is due to the many new competitors that have emerged with a price-cutting strategy without regard to the quality of work. When bidding on projects, they bid at low prices without considering the aspects of cost, quality, time properly, while PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi with years of experience in the construction sector is more careful and implements risk management in every project he will follow, so that with the emergence of new competitors this can be a threat to the continuity of PT. Murni Nira Konstruksi.

Based on the description of business competition that has been applied by PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi, the researchers are interested in studying a strategy that makes the company superior and successful in business competition.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Strategic Management

Strategic management is a process to achieve strategic competitiveness and earn above-average profits. Strategic competitiveness is achieved when a company has developed and learned how to implement a value creation strategy. Above-average returns (exceeding what investors would expect from other investments with a similar level of risk) provide the foundation a company needs that simultaneously satisfies all stakeholders. (Michael Hitt: 2007)

Strategic management is the focus of the organization on the problem of how to create and create a sustainable competitive advantage for the organization, because strategic management is a set of activities such as strategy analysis, strategy design. Systematic implementation and monitoring that can manage resources so that they are in line with the company's vision, mission and overall strategy. Strategic management is not only predicting the future, but also to prepare the company in determining strategic steps and implementation (Hanasini Athapaththu: 2016).

B. Strategic Planning

Steiner 1979, describes at great length about the definition and understanding of strategic planning, even starting from quite a lot of synonyms that have the same meaning. Among them are terms such as comprehensive corporate planning, comprehensive managerial planning, total overall planning, long-range planning, formal planning, comprehensive integrated planning, corporate planning, strategic planning, and a combination of these words all refer to the same meaning of strategic planning. (Kerzner, H., 2001).

Steiner revealed that all managers will definitely state the need for "strategic planning". However, the form can be intuitive-anticipatory or formal strategic planning. Many companies or organizations in their strategy put forward the genius intuition of their main leaders without using formal means in forming strategic plans and many have succeeded brilliantly, although many also had to resign. But how many organizations have the blessing of a genius-intuitive leader? And can it be sustainable? Then, Steiner focused on formal strategic planning as the focus of his book as strategic planning (Priscilla Natasha and Devie, (2013).

According to Steiner, formal strategic planning must have four points of view, namely: future of current decisions, process, attitude philosophy, and system structure.

First, planning is concerned with the future (futura) of current decisions. This means that strategic planning looks at the chain of cause and effect consequences over time the actual or intended decisions that managers will make. The essence of formal strategic planning is the systematic identification of opportunities and threats that exist in the future, which combined with other relevant data provides the basis for companies to make better decisions today to take advantage of opportunities and to avoid threats.

Second, strategic planning is a process. It is a process that begins with setting organizational goals, defining strategies and policies to achieve them, and developing detailed plans to ensure that the strategies are implemented so as to achieve the sought goals.

Third, strategic planning is an attitude. Strategic planning is more of a thought process, intellectual exercise, rather than a prescribed procedure structure or bureaucratic process. For best results, managers and staff in an organization must believe that strategic planning is feasible and must want to do it to the best of their ability.

Fourth, the formal strategic planning system links the main types of plans: strategic plans, medium-term programs, short-term budgets and operating plans. (Priscilla Natasha and Devie, 2013).

C. Vision and Mission

Fred David (2015) states that developing a vision statement is often considered the first step in strategic planning, prior to developing a mission statement. In developing a vision statement will answer the question "what will we become". While the mission statement poses the basic question that all strategists will face: "what is our

business product?'. A clear mission statement explains the values and priorities of the organization. Developing a mission statement forces strategists to think about the nature and scope of current operations and measure potential market attractiveness and future activities.

D. Strategic Formulation Analytical Framework

Fred David (2015), that strategy makers (academics and practitioners) will certainly not consider all alternative actions to be implemented to benefit the company, because the actions that may be taken are countless. Therefore, the

most attractive set of alternative strategies that can be managed should be developed, examined, prioritized and selected. So the advantages, disadvantages, trade-offs, costs, and benefits of this strategy must be determined. Important strategy formulation techniques can be integrated into three strategic formulation analytical frameworks; namely Stage 1 - Input Stage, Stage 2 - Matching/Processing Stage and Stage 3 - Decision Stage. The analytical framework for this strategy formulation is illustrated as follows:

Fig. 2: Strategy Formulation Analytical Framework

(Fred David, 2015)

a) Input Stage

This stage summarizes the basic input information needed for strategy formulation. Procedure for developing EFE (External Factor Evaluation) -IFE (Internal Factor Evaluation) matrix and CPM (Competitive Profile Matrix). The information derived from the EFE-IFE matrix and the CPM provides the basic input information for the matching stage and decision stage matrices. At the input stage, it requires strategists to measure subjectivity during the early stages of the formulation process to generate, evaluate, and select several alternative strategies.

b) Matching Stage – Processing

Strategy is sometimes defined as an organization's ability to match its internal resources and skills in seeing opportunities, as well as risks caused by external factors. The matching stage of the framework and strategy formulation consists of several techniques that can be used such as; SWOT matrix, SPACE matrix, BCG matrix, IE matrix, and Grand Strategy matrix. These tools relate to the information that comes from the input stage in matching external opportunities and threats with internal strengths and weaknesses. Aligning external and internal factors is important to come up with a viable and effective alternative strategy.

c) Decision Stage

This stage involves the Quantitative Strategic Planning Matrix (QSPM) technique. The QSPM uses the input information from Phase 1 to objectively evaluate the alternative strategies identified in Phase 2. The QSPM reveals the relative attractiveness of alternative strategies and provides an objective basis for selecting a particular strategy.

E. Implementation of Strategic

Wheelen and Hunger (2012) state that strategy implementation is a number of activities required for the implementation of strategic planning. Therefore, implementing strategy requires making ideas, decisions, plans, policies, goals and other aspects to be applied in action.

Even the most perfect strategic plan is technically useless unless it is implemented. Change comes through implementation and evaluation, not through planning. A technically imperfect plan that is executed well will achieve more than a perfect plan that is simply typed out without being executed. (Fred and Forest David, 2015).

F. Balanced Scorecard

The four measures of each perspective of the BSC model show relevance to accomplishing the vision and strategy of the organization.

Fig. 3: The causal relationship of the 4 Perspectives of the Balanced Score Card

Fig. 4: The Four Perspectives of the Balanced Score Card related to the Vision and Mission (Source: Kaplan, 1996)

The theoretical framework that describes the influence of funding and investment decisions on competitiveness is as follows (Figure 5):

Fig. 5: Research Model

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research uses descriptive qualitative with analytical methods. Sugiyono (2015: 15) explains the meaning of qualitative research as follows: Qualitative research methods are research methods based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine the condition of natural objects, (as opposed to experiments) where the researcher is the key instrument, sampling data sources are

purposive and snowball, combining techniques with triangulation (combined), data analysis is inductive/qualitative, and qualitative research results emphasize meaning rather than generalization. In accordance with the research objectives, this research will capture, facilitate and describe the results of research on the business strategy planning of PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In carrying out its business processes, PT NMK is headed by a Manager Representative (MR) who is responsible for all activities that occur at PT NMK to the Board of Directors (BOD). PT NMK consists of five (3) divisions, namely:

- Project and Technical Division, which carries out duties and responsibilities for the course of project work, this division oversees Project Manager, Finance Manager, HRD Manager, Site Manager, Technical Operation, Project Admin, Purchasing, Tender Specialist and Health Safety Environment (HSE)
- Marketing and Project Support Division, which performs the duties and responsibilities of marketing to get work/projects and non-technical support for the course of project work.
- Facility Support Division, which performs the duties and responsibilities of work/projects that require fabrication at the PT NMK Workshop. This division supervises the Workshop Manager and Workshop Admin.

A. Analisa IFE – EFE Matrix

It can be seen from the total score weighted in the internal factor evaluation matrix at PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi, namely the IFE score of 3.02 which consists of 1.97 a strength score and 1.05 which is a weakness score. Therefore, NMK companies are classified as being in a strong position internally.

The results of the evaluation of PT NMK's external factors showed a score of 2.88 which consisted of 1.52 opportunity scores and 1.36 which was a challenge score. Therefore, NMK companies are classified as being in a moderate position in responding to external factors, while the numbers 3.0 to 4.0 indicate that the organization responds to external factors very highly (David, 2011).

With the matrix score weighting numbers as seen in the IFE and EFE scores at PT NMK with the IFE (3.02) and EFE (2.88) scores being in the upper quadrant II. This reference table explains that PT. Nira Murni Construction is currently in a growth position. Companies in this position have a strategy that generally applies a horizontal strategy and has the opportunity to grow, concentrating on horizontal integration, continuing to improve on its internal aspects in order to remain competitive in the market controlled by careful feasibility calculations. The growth matrix strategy describes 4 strategies, namely Market Penetration, Product Development, Market Development, and Diversification.

B. Competitive Profile Matrix Analysis– CPM (Benchmarking)

Analysis with the Competitive Profile Matrix (CPM) is intended to identify the company's main competitors on the strengths and weaknesses of these competitors related to the company's competitive strategic position. For this analysis, two competitors have been selected from construction service companies that often meet during tenders in the oil and gas sector, namely PT. XX and PT XY.

The results of the CPM analysis show the position of PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi was in second place at 3.02, slightly below PT EJJV 2.76 and above PT XX 3.42. From the key factors in the context of oil and gas competition, PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi can compete well, especially in terms of profitability and the ability to carry out operations in remote areas. This is because PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi has a leaner and more agile organizational structure and has the ability to handle field operations well. Disadvantages of PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi's main priority compared to its competitors is in terms of service and product development and the lack of employee productivity management, causing some work to be completed on time. This can then be used as input to make future strategies to be more sustainable.

C. SWOT analysis

The results of the SWOT analysis produce the company's work program and are used as a work reference for each department to achieve the goals of PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi. Based on the results of the analysis above, management also makes decisions on strategic steps for continuous improvement for the progress of the company. From the results of the SWOT analysis, PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi also mapped the analysis using the TOWS Matrix to see the right strategy in combining the elements: Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats. So the research results from TOWS analysis produce strategies, namely:

- Strengths Opportunities (SO), namely continuing the existing market segment in oil and gas in remote projects to be able to compete with big company competitors, optimizing workshop fabrication facilities to carry out non-routine work outside the current contract so that they can generate more revenue, maintain good relationships with clients as well as improve networking and relations as widely as possible, and start entering for the development of market segments such as jobs in manufacturing, markets in coal mines and infrastructure both private and government
- Weakness Opportunities (WO) consists of improving and preparing competent and sustainable Human Resources and providing an integrated management system such as Enterprise Resources Planning (ERP) software to facilitate planning, control and performance evaluation in all divisions of the company.
- Strengths Threats (ST) consists of a Cost Leadership strategy to be able to produce competitive prices while maintaining service quality by optimizing direct costs, especially in labor costs and material supply, so that they will be able to compete with other construction service companies.
- Weakness Threats (WT) consists of special developments for the marketing team towards better contract control, to be able to support market development.

From the results of the TOWS analysis above, the resulting alternative strategies will be included in the QSPM as follows:

- Strategy 1: Program me existing market and market development
- Strategy 2: Cost leadership program

- Strategy 3: Human resource development program (HR) and an integrated system (Enterprise Resources Planning)

D. SPACE Matrix Analysis

From the analysis of the SPACE matrix, it was found that the recommended strategy is aggressive at the lower rightmost limit of the quadrant approaching the conservative quadrant. This was translated by the FGD team during the discussion, PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi in the short term, its strategy will be to aggressively maintain performance in the old market, however, be prepared to enter more into new markets and develop new products in the long term with careful feasibility calculations. Thus the choice of aggressive action is not recommended in the short term. In the discussion it was also found that this condition needs to be evaluated every year to see the validity of the strategy.

In qualitative analysis, the Grand Matrix strategy is described as follows.

- Market growth: growing conservatively. If viewed from the productivity of each year, PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi is in a fairly good growth position, although you can say it is not rapid growth, the growth is quite good. The development of the company's productivity has increased since 2016 from 0.36 to 0.40% in 2017, decreased to 0.36% in 2018, increased in 2019 to 0.49% and decreased to 0.28% in in 2020. Oil and gas is suspected to be declining in line with oil and gas production which continues to fall, but PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi proved to be able to compete because

competitors PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi. The average construction cost (corporate overhead) is large and the market target is more diverse, so that in the medium term, it is estimated that in the next 3-4 years, it is estimated that PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi can still maintain its focus on this market.

- Competitive position: slightly competitive. Major construction service players fill the oil and gas market niche, such as state-owned construction companies. When viewed from the size of the assets and the name of the competitor, the position of PT. Nira Murni The smallest construction organization & asset. However, in the oil and gas project niche, PT. Nira Murni Konstruksi can compete well in terms of contracts won alternately with big players. Operational capability of PT. Nira Murni Construction in remote areas that is proven to be good with quite competitive operating expenses, Nira Murni Konstruksi can compete by participating in selected tenders with good feasibility

Based on the analysis, the position of PT Nira Murni Konstruksi on the Grand Matrix Analysis is in quadrant 1 as shown in Figure 6. PT NMK's position in the Grand Matrix Strategy. In Quadrant 1, the general strategies suggested are market development, market penetration, product development, forward or backward or horizontal integration and related diversification.

Fig. 6: PT NMK's position in the Grand Matrix Strategy

In the process of analyzing the QSPM decision, the two alternative strategies are compared by giving an attractiveness score (AS) on external and internal key factors relevant to the choice of strategy, then multiplied into a total attractiveness score (TAS).

In the QSPM analysis, the total attractiveness score - the largest TAS is 5.90 in the existing market and development market strategy. This shows that PT NMK must focus on a strategy to continue the market in oil and gas and carry out market development which is a strategy to increase the market for an existing product or service through more vigorous and larger marketing efforts (David, R, 2004).

NMK carried out this strategy as evidenced by the addition of marketing in the year until 2021, namely an increase in the number of project work in Oil and Gas where several large contracts have been obtained by PT NMK. However, this market development strategy must be started and developed to keep the company in a growth position. This is done by establishing good cooperation with old clients and seeking new clients such as developing market share to manufacturing companies such as shipping, chemical and market segments such as infrastructure projects. government with a good feasibility process. While the total attractiveness score – the second TAS of 5.17 is a cost leadership strategy. This strategy is a strategy that aims to make the company

prioritize cost leadership so that it can optimize so that it can continue to compete with other construction service companies. PT NMK must continue to optimize the company's costs below its competitors while at the same time and still offering adequate value. Then the total attractiveness score – the third TAS of 5.00 is the Human Resources Development strategy and System Enterprise Resources Planning. This strategy aims to prepare competent human resources to face the challenges that will come. The company will be able to provide quality products or services so that it will improve a positive image and increase the effectiveness and efficiency of employees' work so that they can achieve the targets set by the company. Meanwhile, the development of an ERP system is needed by the Company to make it easier for companies to manage single and real-time data.

Changes in data in one section, will affect the recording in other related sections. This synchronization of processes in a number of related departments helps work to achieve faster and better results as well as as a basis for fast and strong decision making so as to further increase the effectiveness and efficiency of employees' work so that they can achieve the targets set by the company.

From the strategies formulated above, then the target is formulated with clear key performance indicators, and an action plan is also formulated. In strategic management and performance management, this is covered by looking at four important perspectives in the balanced score card, namely the financial perspective, the customer perspective, the internal process perspective and the learning perspective.

Balanced Score Card		
Perspektif	Action Plan	Measurement or Target of KPI
Financial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain monthly and annual sales. • Direct cost efficiency with good quality and quantity supply control from suppliers. • Increase cash generation • Increase annual sales growth • Improve the effectiveness of asset management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable sales with a minimum total of 120 billion Rupiah per year. • Minimum gross profit of 15%. • Invoice process maximum 30 days per month. • Annual Sales increase of 20% • Increased Return on Assets
Customer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain service delivery according to the standards required by the contract. • Improve accuracy in the completion of project work with good quality. • Increase the number of new customers by promoting the performance of PT NMK to prospective customers in oil and gas projects. • Maintain good relationship communication with customers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer satisfaction with KPI service acceptance standards >85%. • Schedule Performance Index (SPI) 1 • Marketing to projects minimum tender 5 times per year. • Monthly regular meetings with customers to discuss performance and improvement ideas.
Internal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Running operations according to company operational standards with leadership assurance by middle & top management. • Ensure that facilities and information technology using the Enterprise Resources Planning system are available and employees are able to use them. • Develop new partnerships or partnerships that are aligned with the core business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management visibility to the target site 4 times annually. • Annual audit of ISO standard no significant findings. • ERP software is available and 100% and Employees are able to use it • Increasing number of new partners per year, Minimum 2 new partners
Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase labor productivity • Improve the competence and expertise of the workforce by strengthening the technostructure organizational part in the field of marketing and development, with a focus on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Contract mastery, learn from previous contracts. o Marketing assessment in the mining area. o Service excellence: training, standards. o Cost optimization. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Schedule Performance Index (SPI) 1 • 100% training or team technostructure training. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Standard commercial & legal checklist for contract bidding that guarantees no contract slippage. ->2nd year. o Road map and assessment results of service contracts to mining and infrastructure companies-- > year 2 initial road map, 3rd year pilot project. • Implementing a technostructure team performance evaluation every 6 months to see competency gaps.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase workforce motivation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% Employee Attendance Rate, is the percentage of the ratio of lost workdays to the number of days employees come to work.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase workforce satisfaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee Satisfaction Index (Staff Satisfaction Index) through surveys at least once a year

Balanced Score Card		
Perspektif	Action Plan	Measurement or Target of KPI
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve internal cooperation climate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100% available Standard Operational Procedure (SOP) and Job Desc • Availability of gathering or team building activities at least once a year.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entering new markets in the mining and infrastructure sector with quite large potential 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot project entering construction services for the mining sector and government infrastructure - → 3rd year. Establish in new markets in 4th year.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSR program with local authorities for minimum social costs and operational disruptions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • minimum unrest from local community.

Table 1: Target in PT NMK's Balanced Score Card

V. CONCLUSION

- Internal External Matrix Analysis shows the position of PT Nira Murni Konstruksi in the upper 2nd quadrant, explaining that PT Nira Murni Konstruksi is in a growth position. Analysis of the Competitive Profile Matrix – CPM compared to two competitors selected in the context of competition in the oil and gas sector shows the position of PT Nira Murni Konstruksi in second place with a score of 3.04, slightly below PT EJJV with a score of 3.08, and above PT Shaftindo Energy with a score of 2.90. From the results of the TOWS analysis, the resulting alternative strategies are the first strategy is a program to maintain the existing market and market development, the second strategy is a cost leadership program and the third strategy is a human resource development program (HR) and an integrated system (Enterprise Resources Planning). Strategic Position Analysis and Action Evaluation. The SPACE matrix shows that PT Nira Murni Konstruksi is in the aggressive quadrant, close to the conservative quadrant. The short term strategy is suggested to maintain performance in the old market and start to develop the market to enter more into new markets and develop new products in the long term with careful feasibility calculation. The analysis of the Grand Matrix Strategy places PT Nira Murni Konstruksi in Quadrant 1. The general strategies suggested are market development, market penetration, product development, forward or backward or horizontal integration and related diversification. QSPM Decision Analysis to analyze strategic alternatives in terms of which marketing is more priority. From the analysis, the results are obtained to focus on alternative strategies to continue to the oil and gas company market and develop into new markets. While the second alternative is the Cost Leadership strategy and the third alternative strategy is the Human Resource Development strategy and System Enterprise Resources Planning.
- The managerial implication in the formulation of the strategic plan from this research is to be able to find out the current position of PT NMK from the results of internal and external analysis so that it can determine the company's next strategic steps and provide a focus on several alternative strategies that must be carried out by the company to be able to compete with service companies other constructions with measurable strategic plan steps

and appropriate feasibility by formulating short-term and long-term company plans with clear achievement targets and indicators.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Athapaththu, H.K.S. Hanasini. (2016). An Overview of Strategic Management: An Analysis of the Concepts and the Importance of Strategic Management. International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 6, Issue 2, (124-126) February 2016
- [2.] Badan Pusat Statistik. (2016). Booklet Indeks Pembangunan Manusia Metode Baru. Jakarta.
- [3.] Fred. R. David, (2004). Manajemen Strategis: Konsep-Konsep, Edisi Kesembilan, Jakarta: PT. Indeks
- [4.] Fred R. David – Forest R. David, (2015). *Strategic Management Concepts and Cases - A Competitive Advantage Approach, ed 15*, Pearson, 2015.
- [5.] Fred, R David. (2011). Strategic Management Manajemen Strategi Konsep,. Edisi 12. Jakarta: Salemba Empat
- [6.] Hitt, M. A., Ireland, R. D., Sirmon, D. G., dan Trahms, C. A. (2007). Strategic entrepreneurship: creating value for individuals, organizations, and society. The Academy of Management Perspectives , 25 (2), 57-75.
- [7.] Hunger, D.J., dan Wheelen, L. Thomas, (2012). Strategic Management and. Business Policy,(13th Edition). United States of America: Pearson
- [8.] Kaplan, Robert & Norton. David P. (1996). Translating Strategy Into Action The Balance Scorecard. Harvard Business School. Boston.
- [9.] Kerzner, H. (2001). Project Management. Seventh Edition. John Wiley & Sons
- [10.] Priscilla Natasha dan Devie, (2013). Analisa Pengaruh Strategic Planning Terhadap Keunggulan Bersaing Dan Kinerja Perusahaan, Business Accounting Review, VOL. 1, NO.2, 2013
- [11.] Sudarto, Budi Soesilo Soepandji, Ismeth Abidin dan Bambang Trigunaryah (2014). Pengembangan Sistem Bisnis Perusahaan Jasa Konstruksi Di Indonesia Dengan Menggunakan Knowledge Base Management System. Institut Teknologi Bandung Departement of Civil Engineering
- [12.] Sugiyono (2015). Metode Penelitian Kombinasi (Mix Methods). Bandung: Alfabeta.